

The environMENTAL Project

GLOSSARY OF KEY TERMS

The environMENTAL Consortium

June 2026

About this Glossary

The [environMENTAL project](#) is an EU funded multidisciplinary research initiative that seeks to understand how environmental factors (including aspects of the built and natural environment, climate-related exposures, and social conditions) influence brain health and mental wellbeing. Bringing together expertise from fields such as neuroscience, mental health, environmental science, artificial intelligence, data science, and genetics, the project relies on effective communication across diverse disciplines and stakeholder groups.

To support this, this glossary has been developed to provide clear and consistent definitions of key terms used throughout the project. It is intended to promote a shared understanding among the researchers and members of the public (including people with lived experience involved in the project).

The glossary was also developed in response to a recommendation arising from the project's [Consensus Conference \(CC\)](#), which highlighted the importance of clearly defining relevant terminology, including key concepts such as mental wellbeing. By providing agreed definitions, the glossary aims to reduce ambiguity and support consistent communication across project activities and outputs.

Many of the concepts included in this glossary are used across multiple disciplines and may be interpreted differently depending on the context. The definitions presented here have been informed by relevant literature and project discussions and are intended to serve as a common reference point within the context of the environMENTAL project. They are not intended to replace established clinical, legal, or disciplinary definitions and should not be regarded as exhaustive. As scientific knowledge and terminology continue to evolve, this glossary may be updated to reflect new evidence and stakeholder perspectives.

Glossary of Key Terms used in environMENTAL

3D Brain Organoids (“Assembloids”)

Small clusters of human brain cells grown from [pluripotent stem cells](#). They develop in ways that resemble real human brain tissue, allowing researchers to study how different types of neurons appear and organise themselves in key brain regions. In practice, this means they can model the mix and arrangement of brain cells found in important “nodes” of brain networks – areas whose specific cell patterns shape how those networks function.

Automated Self-Therapy

This is a technology-based mental health intervention where an individual interacts with an artificial intelligence (AI) system instead of a human counsellor to manage psychological distress.

In the context of the environMENTAL project, this involves using [Virtual Reality \(VR\)](#) to facilitate "embodied self-conversations" where a participant can sequentially occupy two different virtual bodies – one representing themselves and another representing a "future self" who has already overcome personal adversity. The AI acts as a virtual therapist, using advanced natural language techniques to provide questions and answers that guide the individual through mental health counselling.

Automated Therapy System

This is a digital tool or software designed to provide mental health support or therapeutic guidance without the need for a human therapist in real time. These systems often use technologies such as chatbots, mobile apps, online platforms, or [Virtual Reality \(VR\)](#) programmes to deliver structured psychological support.

Biomarkers

Biological signals (such as brain-scan patterns, blood markers, or genetic features) that help predict vulnerability or resilience to environmental stress.

Centiles

Centiles, also called percentiles, are a way of describing how a value compares to others in a group.

In environMENTAL they often refer to a statistical way of comparing an individual's biological or brain data to a large group. Being in the 70th centile means you score higher than 70% of people.

Cellular Mechanisms of Molecular Signatures

The biological processes inside cells that reflect the molecular changes caused by environmental adversity or challenges.

ChatGPT

An AI language model that generates human-like text. The project's automated therapy system uses similar technology to deliver supportive dialogue in [Virtual Reality \(VR\)](#).

Cohort

A large group of people who are followed over time for research. These cohorts provide [multimodal data](#), meaning information collected from many different sources (such as brain scans, genetics, behaviour, environment, and mental-health assessments) to understand how the environment and biology interact across development. Examples used in the environMENTAL project include IMAGEN and STRATIFY

CRHR1 (Corticotropin Releasing Hormone Receptor 1)

A gene that produces a receptor on the cell surface involved in the body's stress-response system. Variations in this gene can influence stress sensitivity and behaviours such as alcohol use.

CRISPR-Based Technology

A precise gene editing tool used to switch genes on or off in stem cells. The project uses it to recreate molecular patterns linked to environmental adversity.

Deep Phenotyping

A detailed way of collecting very detailed information (e.g. behavioural, biological, psychological, social, and genetic) to understand how environmental exposure affects the brain.

Digital Health Apps

Smartphone tools that track mental health and daily experiences using self-reports and sensor data.

Diffusion Tensor Imaging (DTI).

A specialised type of [MRI \(Magnetic Resonance Imaging\) scan](#). MRI uses strong magnets and radio waves to create detailed pictures of the brain. DTI builds on this by showing how different brain regions are connected through white matter pathways, which act like communication cables in the brain.

DNA Methylation

A chemical modification of DNA (the genetic material that carries the instructions for how our bodies develop and function). Methylation acts like a switch that helps turn genes on or off without changing the DNA sequence itself. Environmental exposure can influence these methylation patterns, which is why the project studies them to understand how adversity affects biological processes linked to mental health.

EEG (Electroencephalogram)

A method that measures electrical activity in the brain. It records the brain's natural electrical signals using small sensors placed on the scalp. These signals show how active different parts of the brain are from moment to moment, helping researchers understand patterns linked to stress, attention, or emotional responses.

Environmental Risk and Resilience Signatures (ERRS)

Patterns in brain and biological data that show how environmental stress relates to symptoms like depression, anxiety, stress, or substance use.

Epigenetics

Epigenetics refers to biological changes that affect how genes are switched on or off without changing the underlying DNA sequence. DNA contains the instructions for how our bodies develop and function, but epigenetic mechanisms – such as DNA methylation – act like dimmer switches that control how strongly those instructions are used. These switches can be influenced by experiences and environmental factors, including stress, pollution, and adversity.

In the environMENTAL project, epigenetics helps explain how environmental exposures can shape brain and mental-health outcomes across development.

eQTLs (Expression Quantitative Trait Loci)

eQTLs are genetic variants that influence gene expression, meaning how much a gene is “turned on” or “turned off.” They help identify which genes are more active or less active in people with certain genetic backgrounds, and how this interacts with environmental exposures.

Expert by Experience (EbE)

An individual who contributes to a project or service based on their personal, lived experience of a particular issue, condition, or system rather than through academic training alone.

In environMENTAL, EbE members contribute to the project based on their experience of mental health challenges, navigating mental health services, or environmental adversity.

FDA (Food and Drug Administration)

The U.S. agency that approves medicines. Some drugs tested in the project are existing FDA-approved compounds being repurposed.

fMRI (Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging)

A brain imaging method that measures blood flow to show which areas of the brain are active.

The environMENTAL project uses "task-based" fMRI to see which brain regions light up while a participant does a specific test (like a memory game), and "resting-state" fMRI to map how different brain areas naturally communicate with each other while the participant is simply relaxing.

Genome

This refers to the complete set of genetic instructions in the cell of a living thing.

Genome-Wide Association Study (GWAS)

A Genome-Wide Association Study is a research approach that examines millions of genetic variants across the whole genome to identify which variants are statistically associated with a particular trait or condition. GWAS compares the DNA of individuals who differ in a trait (such as brain structure, stress sensitivity, or risk for a mental-health disorder) to find variants that occur more frequently in one group than another.

Neuroendocrine

This refers to the way the brain (neuro) and the hormone producing glands (endocrine) work together to control the body. It describes systems where the brain sends signals that trigger the release of hormones into the bloodstream, which then affect organs throughout the body.

HPA System (Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal System)

The core [neuroendocrine](#) pathway that coordinates the body's response to stress. It begins in the brain, where the hypothalamus detects threat or challenge and signals the pituitary gland. The pituitary then releases hormones that stimulate the adrenal glands to produce cortisol, the body's primary stress hormone. Cortisol mobilises energy, sharpens attention, and helps the body cope with immediate demands. Once the stressor passes, feedback loops reduce hormone release and return the system to baseline.

Human Embryonic Stem Cells (hESC)

Special cells taken from very early-stage embryos that can be developed into any type of cell in the human body. Because they are so flexible, scientists use them to study how organs form, how diseases develop, and how different cell types behave. They are one of the most powerful tools for understanding human biology.

Induced Pluripotent Stem Cells (iPSC)

Adult cells (like skin cells) are reprogrammed back into a stem-cell-like state so they can again become any cell type, including neurons.

Mental Health

A person's emotional, psychological, and social wellbeing – how they think, feel, and act in daily life. It shapes how people handle stress, relate to others, make decisions, and manage challenges. Good mental health does not mean feeling positive all the time; it means having the capacity to cope with difficulties, recover from setbacks, and function in ways that feel meaningful and connected. Mental health is influenced by a combination of biological factors, life experiences, and environmental conditions

Mental Wellbeing

A person's overall quality of life and ability to cope with challenges, including resilience and fulfillment.

Molecular Signatures

Patterns in molecules – such as proteins, gene expression, or DNA methylation—that reflect how environmental adversity affects the brain.

mQTLs (Methylation Quantitative Trait Loci)

mQTLs are genetic variants that influence DNA methylation, the chemical markings that help switch genes on or off. They show how inherited DNA differences shape a person's epigenetic patterns. This matters because environmental stress can also alter methylation, so mQTLs help separate genetic influences from environmental effects.

Multi Modal Omics Analyses

A combined analysis of many biological layers – genes, gene expression, proteins, and epigenetics – to understand how environmental adversity affects the body.

Multimodal Data

Data collected from many different sources – brain scans, genetics, behaviour, environment, and more – to build a complete picture of how environmental stress affects mental health.

Multimodal Environmental Signatures

Patterns that combine different types of environmental data (e.g., pollution, noise, climate, urbanicity) to understand how the environment affects mental health.

Neurobiological Markers

Biological signals from the brain that help researchers understand how mental processes, stress responses, or emotional states are functioning. These markers act as indicators of how the brain is developing, how it responds to environmental stress, and whether certain systems (such as emotion regulation or attention) are working differently from expected patterns.

Neurocognitive Model

A model that integrates environmental, biological, and brain-imaging data to explain how environmental stress leads to mental-health symptoms.

Neuroendocrinological Stress Mechanism

A neuroendocrinological stress mechanism is the combined brain–hormone system that activates when a person experiences stress. It involves communication between key brain regions (such as the amygdala, hippocampus, and hypothalamus) and the endocrine system, which releases hormones into the bloodstream.

The best-known pathway is the [HPA axis \(Hypothalamic–Pituitary–Adrenal axis\)](#). When activated, it triggers the release of stress hormones like cortisol, which help the body respond to challenges. Over time, repeated or chronic activation of this system can influence brain development, emotional regulation, and mental-health outcomes.

Neuroinformatics Platform (e.g., The Virtual Brain)

A computer system that simulates how large-scale brain networks behave, helping researchers test how environmental stress might change brain activity. For example, [The Virtual Brain \(TVB\) platform](#) – an open-source platform for constructing and simulating personalised brain network models.

Neuronal Phenotype

The distinct features that characterise a specific type of neuron, including its shape, the genes it expresses, the neurotransmitters it uses, and how it connects and communicates with other cells. These features determine the neuron's role in a brain network, for example, whether it excites or inhibits other neurons, how fast it fires, and which circuits it participates in. Environmental factors, including stress, can influence aspects of neuronal phenotype during development, shaping how brain functions.

Non-Genetic Exposures

This refers to all the influences in a person's life that come from outside their DNA. They include the environments we grow up in, the experiences we have, the people around us, and the physical conditions we're exposed to. These factors can shape health, behaviour, and development just as powerfully as genetics – sometimes even more so.

Normative Models

Statistical models that compare an individual's brain or biological data to a large reference group to identify unusual patterns.

Pharmacological Compounds

Drugs or chemical substances used to prevent, diagnose or treat diseases.

In the environMENTAL project, some pharmacological compounds are tested to see whether they can reverse harmful brain-cell changes caused by environmental stress.

Plasma Membrane Receptor

A plasma membrane receptor is a specialised protein embedded in the cell's outer membrane that allows the cell to sense and respond to signals in its environment. These

receptors recognise specific molecules (such as hormones, neurotransmitters, or immune signals) binding to them like a lock and key. When activated, they trigger internal signalling pathways that change how the cell behaves, communicates, or adapts. In the brain, plasma membrane receptors help neurons receive chemical messages, regulate activity, and respond to stress-related hormones.

Pluripotent Stem Cells

Pluripotent stem cells are cells that can develop into all cell types found in the human body, including neurons, muscle cells, blood cells, and many others. They have two defining features: they can self-renew (make more of themselves), and they can differentiate into any specialised cell type except those needed to form an entire embryo. This makes them essential for studying human development, modelling diseases, and creating lab-grown tissues such as brain organoids.

Proteomics

Proteomics is the systematic study of the full set of proteins (the proteome) present in a cell, tissue, or biological sample. Proteins carry out most of the cell's work – they act as enzymes, receptors, structural components, and signalling molecules.

By measuring which proteins are present, how abundant they are, and how they are modified, proteomics reveals how cells respond to environmental conditions such as stress, inflammation, or pollution. Because proteins reflect real-time cellular activity, proteomics provides a dynamic picture of biological processes that cannot be seen from DNA alone.

Reinforcement Learning (RL)

Reinforcement Learning is a computational framework that describes how behaviour is shaped by rewards, punishments, and feedback from the environment. An individual (or an algorithm) takes an action, observes the outcome, and updates future behaviour based on whether the outcome was better or worse than expected. Over time, this trial-and-error process helps the learner discover which actions lead to the most beneficial results.

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

An approach that ensures research and technological development are carried out in ways that are ethical, transparent, inclusive, and socially beneficial. It encourages researchers to anticipate potential impacts, reflect on their assumptions and choices, involve diverse stakeholders (including the public), and adapt their work in response to societal needs and concerns. RRI aims to align scientific progress with broader public values, promoting trust, accountability, and long-term positive outcomes.

Severe Mental Illness (SMI)

Severe Mental Illness describes mental-health conditions that cause substantial and persistent difficulties in thinking, feeling, or relating to others, and that markedly interfere with daily life. These conditions typically involve episodes of acute symptoms as well as long-term challenges that may require coordinated medical, psychological, and social support. SMI is a classification used in healthcare and research to identify individuals who may need more intensive or specialised services.

Spatiotemporal Data

Spatiotemporal data refers to information that includes both spatial location and temporal timing, allowing researchers to track how patterns evolve across places and over time. Each data point has coordinates (e.g., GPS location, brain region, neighbourhood) and a timestamp (e.g., moment, day, developmental stage). This type of data is essential for analysing dynamic processes such as environmental exposures, mobility patterns, brain activity, or symptom trajectories.

Statistical Inferences

Statistical inference refers to the methods used to make evidence-based conclusions about a population or underlying process using data from a sample. Because researchers rarely observe everything directly, they use probability models to estimate patterns, test hypotheses, and quantify how confident they can be in their conclusions. Statistical inference helps determine whether observed effects (such as associations between environmental stress and brain markers) are likely to reflect real underlying relationships rather than random variation.

Stem Cells

Stem cells are special cells that can develop into many different types of cells in the body. Unlike most cells, which have a fixed role (such as skin cells or neurons), stem cells can either stay as stem cells or transform into specialised cells depending on what the body needs. This ability makes them essential for studying human development, modelling diseases, and creating lab-grown tissues such as 3D brain organoids.

Stratification

The process of organising a population or dataset into meaningful subgroups or categories based on shared characteristics (such as age, sex, socioeconomic status, genetic ancestry, or exposure level). By analysing these strata separately or adjusting for them statistically, researchers can distinguish genuine effects from those attributed to underlying group differences.

Transcriptome-Wide Association Studies (TWAS)

Analytical methods that combine genome-wide association study (GWAS) data with gene-expression data to identify genes whose predicted expression is associated with a trait or disorder. Instead of testing millions of genetic variants individually, TWAS estimates how genetic variation influences gene expression in specific tissues and then tests whether those genetically regulated expression levels relate to outcomes such as mental-health symptoms, brain structure, or environmental sensitivity.

Transdiagnostic Symptoms

Psychological or behavioural features that appear across multiple mental-health conditions, rather than being specific to a single diagnosis. Examples include anxiety, sleep problems, irritability, cognitive difficulties, or social withdrawal. These symptoms cut across traditional diagnostic categories and often reflect underlying processes – such as stress reactivity, emotion regulation, or cognitive control – that are shared across disorders.

Urbanicity

A measure of how “urban” an environment is, including population density built up space, and socioeconomic factors.

UrbanSat

A measure of how “urban” a place is based on data derived from satellite images. Instead of just saying an area is urban or rural, [UrbanSat](#) looks at 11 different features – such as how many buildings there are, how bright the area is at night, how many people live there, and how much green space is around. By combining all these pieces, it creates a detailed picture of what a neighbourhood is like.

One of the biggest projects using UrbanSat is the [Adolescent Brain Cognitive Development \(ABCD\) Study](#), which follows more than 11,000 children across the United States. By linking satellite data to children’s health and brain-imaging data, researchers can explore how things like noise, crowding, green space, or heat might shape development over time.

The Virtual Brain (TVB)

The [Virtual Brain \(TVB\)](#) is a computer platform that creates simulated models of how a person’s brain works. It uses information from brain scans (such as the shape of the brain, how different regions are connected, and how they communicate) to build a personalised “virtual” version of someone’s brain. Researchers can then use this virtual brain to explore how activity spreads through the brain, how different regions interact, and how changes in one area might affect the whole system.

Virtual Reality (VR)

A computer-generated 3D environment that people can explore using a headset.

The environMENTAL project uses VR to recreate stressful environmental conditions and teach coping strategies.

White Matter

This refers to the communication network of the brain and spinal cord. It is a network of long, thin nerve fibres that connect different brain regions.

Funding Acknowledgement

Funded by the European Union. Complementary funding was received by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee (10041392 and 10038599). Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA) or UKRI. Neither the European Union nor HADEA nor UKRI can be held responsible for them.

Suggested citation:

Ogoh, G., Bernd, S. and the environMENTAL Consortium (2026) The environMENTAL Project Glossary of Key Terms. Nottingham: University of Nottingham. <https://10.5281/zenodo.20601655>